

ANALYSIS OF TRANSPOSITION OF WORD GROUPS

Shodieva Gulrukh Nazir kizi

Teacher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367653>

Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of transposition of word groups in linguistics, including English. The article is analyzed with the help of a number of scientists' opinions and examples.*

Keywords: *Transposition, vocabulary, linguistics, English language, grammar.*

INTRODUCTION

The transfer of a word group - transposition means that a word belonging to a certain group weakens its specific meaning and function, and acquires a semantic and grammatical sign specific to another word group. In Turkic languages, word groups are not strictly separated from each other, they are connected and form a whole system. The parts of this system are connected with words that are evaluated as hybrid words based on the law of "intermediate third" in dialectical logic, retain the semantic-grammatical characteristics of both types, and are in the stage of transition from one category to another category.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The English linguist G. Leach puts forward the idea of looking at indirect speech acts as a special speech strategy called the strategy of bites. [1] This strategy consists in the fact that the expressed illocutionary act acts as an assistant in the realization of another illocutionary act. The effectiveness of such indirect speech acts is based on the influence of the principle of relevance. In this case, the listener perceives the existing speech act as a primary illocutionary act that "lays the ground" for the next speech illocutionary act. In order to further develop the division of indirect speech acts into conventional and non-conventional groups, Pospelova proposed a detailed classification and divided these two groups of speech acts into mono-intentional (one-purpose) patterns and two types of poly-intentional (multi-purpose) indirect speech structures: modeled, structural and implicative. [2]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DISCUSSION

Scientific research on the issue of transposition of word groups and word formation in English is very important. The reason is that the transition of a word from one category to another leads to the emergence of a new word belonging to a different lexical-grammatical category, and this process, in turn, is closely related to word formation.

Conjugation of verb forms is a special model of transposition, according to which the present and past tense bases and adjective forms of simple, prefixed and compound verbs are separated from the verb and adjective system (paradigm) into the noun system. passes. [3]

At the level of speech, this appearance of verb forms has a new position.

The concept of transposition was first introduced into scientific circulation in the 30s of the last century by the French linguist S.Bally to express the mechanism of the transition of a word (or base) from one word group to another: we are talking about the transposition of a linguistic symbol, which plays the role of a symbol belonging to another category while preserving the numbers". [4]

He distinguishes between two types of transposition:

1) change of the initial syntactic function without changing the lexical meaning of the symbol - functional

2) acquiring a new lexical meaning in parallel with the syntactic function of the word - semantic transposition.

These two types were then compared as lexical and syntactic derivations. [5] The issue of conversion was covered for the first time in the works of A.I. Smirnitsky. According to him, the word-making tool in conversion consists only of the word paradigm. [6]

This interpretation is reflected in the comment "conversion" in the dictionary of O.S. Akhmanova. [7] Under the term "hypostasis", transposition is interpreted as the transfer of one word group to another word group in a broad sense (including substantivation and adjectivization) by means of conversion. [8]

So, in linguistics, the concept of transposition means a broader concept than conversion. That is, in conversion, the main word-forming tool is word paradigms, and in transposition, it is understood that the word moves from one category to another category. This is a linguistic phenomenon that changes not only the lexical, but also the syntactic function of words.

RESULTS

The stylistic effect is based on the formation of a synonymous line consisting of several syntactic constructions with emotional, expressive coloring and one neutral syntactic construction made using traditional syntactic relations. In their work, M.D. Kuznets and Y.M. Skrebneva grouped together syntactic devices that increase the effectiveness of speech, together with their appearance in cases that are not according to the rule. Based on the principles of these authors, we consider syntactic units in the following sequence:

Inversion (change of the usual sentence order);

Transposition (changing the position of syntactic devices);

Repetition (introduction of elements that do not bring new information: polysyndeton, chiasm, anadiplosis);

Omission of necessary elements (asyndeton, ellipsis);

Input structures.

In English, each part of a sentence has its usual place according to the type of sentence and syntactic expression. Let's take a look at the example of a sentence.

In some cases, this strict order in the sentence can be changed.

1. If the sentence "there is" is used, the reverse word order is used:

There is table in that room.

2. If the author's sentence comes after the quoted sentence:

"I'm glad to see you", said the old man kindly. (VSO)

3. In sentences with the possessive noun associated with the adverbs "Here, there":

Here is the book you are looking for. (OSV)

But: in the above two cases, if the subject of the sentence is given by personal pronouns, the correct word order is used:

"I don't smoke", he said.

Here he comes.

4. In participle sentences that begin with a case and are expressed by a noun with possessive intransitive verbs:

From the window came the sounds of music.

Inversion (lat. "overturning, replacing") is a syntactic method, a stylistic figure, based on changing the usual order of the parts of a sentence. Inversion is used for purposes such as emphatic or logical separation of any word or phrase in a sentence, rhythmic intonation organization of poetic speech.

CONCLUSION

Each of the above sentence types has its own form and intonation. At the same time, any one of the above sentence types can express the meaning of the others. Such words reflect a special modality, a certain stylistic color and impressiveness. For example, a sentence that is a prepositional phrase can be interrogative. Such statements show that the questioner guesses what the answer will be and that he is not indifferent to the answer.

REFERENCES

1. Leech G. Politeness: Is there an East-West Divide? In: Journal of Foreign Languages, Shanghai, 2005. . –311 p.
2. Поспелова А.Г. Косвенные высказывания// Спорные вопросы английской грамматики. – Л., 1988. –. 187p
3. Alimova Kh. Dari Word-forming Transposition Phenomenon // International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, December 2020, Volume 12, Supplementary Issue 3. – P. 516-521. ISSN 0975-2366. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31838/ijpr/2020.SP3.070>
4. Взаимонаправленная транспозиция ‘имя лица – признак лица’ в русском и английском языках// Библиотечный каталог российских и украинских диссертаций, 2004 (Interdirectional transposition ‘face name – face feature’ in Russian and English // Library Catalogue of Russian and Ukrainian Dissertations, 2004) // www.rus-lang.com
5. Кубрякова Е.С. Типы языковых значений. Семантика производного слова. – М.: Наука, 1981. – 146 с. (Kubryakova E.S. Types of linguistic meanings. Semantics of the derivative word. Moscow, Nauka, 1981, 146 p.)
6. Кубрякова Е.С. Что такое словообразование. – М.: Наука, 1965. – 70 с. (Kubryakova E.S. What is word-formation. Moscow, Nauka, 1965, 70 p.)
7. Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. – М.: Советская энциклопедия, 1966. 202с. (Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of Linguistic Terms. Moscow, Soviet Encyclopedia, 1966, 202 p.)
8. Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. – М.: Советская энциклопедия, 1966. 100с. (Akhmanova O.S. Dictionary of Linguistic Terms. Moscow, Soviet Encyclopedia, 1966, 100 p.)